

Application of Floating Maxim on Implicature in Japanese Language

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ABSTRACT: Cooperative principle is a principle in communication to make speakers and listeners to be coordinative for achieve communication's aims. In cooperative principle, there are maxims accordance cooperative principle. Speakers must give truth speech, be brief, do not more informative than its required, and make it clear. Sometimes people didn't contribute in communication, and make utterance float the maxims. This floating maxim creates the implicature. Implicature is one of pragmatic's scope discussed about conveyed meaning in utterances. Meanwhile pragmatic is a scope of speakers meaning which implicature has truth conditional meaning conveyed by speakers. But, only conversational implicature create by floating maxim. Implicature can be find in every language such as Japanese. It supported by ideology called *aimai* to make ambiguous speech. As the background, this research is to find floating maxim in implicature in Japanese. Floating maxims by Grice used for theory in this research. The method that used was descriptive analysis. Data source in *anime* and Japanese drama to find implicature in Japanese. The result of this research is maxim of relation were founded dominant. It according to the aims of communication, and other side speaker has different aims with their partner. Floating of relation maxim used for for showing disinterest, admiration, and sarcasm.

KEYWORD: implicature, floating maxim, japanese language, pragmatic.

INTRODUCTION

Implicature is one of scope in pragmatic. Pragmatic is a study in linguistic about speakers meaning, and what is speakers wanted in utterance (Morris, 1938; Saul, 2010). As one of scopes in pragmatic, implicature study about what is the truth conditional in utterance (Horn, 2004: 03). Grice (1975: 44) stated in implicature there are implicature (the noun), what is implicate (the verb), and implicatum (what is implied). In implicature, the truth meaning conveyed in the phrase. This make meaning of implicature different to meaning of phrase. According to the mode of sentences, there are declarative, imperative, and interrogative. The mode of utterance may form in interrogative, but the truth meaning may to request something or to command as in imperative.

Grice (1975) categorized implicature as two group, first conversational implicature and the second conventional implicature. When implicature appear in exchange conversational process, called conversational implicature. But when implicature appear in specific word indicated to conveyed meaning and not always create in conversational process, it called conventional implicature. The conversational implicature often occurs in communication. When participant engage in conversation, they exchange their position as speaker and participant until reach the aims of conversation. Then, the exchange of position formulated a principle called cooperative principle.

Cooperative principle is a principle in communication to make conversational contribution as required according to the purpose of the talk exchange in which engaged (Grice, 1975: 45). Cooperative principle is one of important to make communication achieved its aims. Both of speaker and listener have to give good contribution while communication. There are four maxims accordance with cooperative principle, such as quality, quantitative, relation, and manner. The category of quality related to the what is believed by speakers based on the reality. Speaker do not say what is believed to be false. Next category, quantitative maxim make speaker to not informative than required. Relative maxim bring speaker to focus and relevant through communication. Next, manner make speaker to be perspicuous, said what have to said, and be orderly (Grice, 1975: 46). For some reason, participant may fail to fulfill maxims. They may quietly to violate maxims or can't fulfill two maxims in one time. For this reason, about participant can't fulfill maxims while exchange conversation may raise conversational implicature as showed below.

(1-1) A: So, can you please come over here again right now

B: **Well, I have to go to Edinburgh today sir**

A: Hmmm. How about this Thursday?

(Levinson, 1983: 48)

The conversation in (1-1) showed that B is not contribute as cooperative principle required. B has violated relevant maxim, because B is not relevant as A said before. A requested B to come at A or soon after conversation, the response that A wanted just B come to that place. But, as B stated “Well, I have to go to Edinburgh today sir” implies that B can’t come to the place and rejected the request showed in “I have to go to Edinburgh today”. In utterance A, there are several assumptions can detect. First, A and B aren’t in the same place; (2) B may possible know where is A, and B has have come to A place before stated in “...come over here again”; (3) A assumed B will accept or reject the request; (4) B has rejected the request. There isn’t relation between requesting to A place and B will go to Edinburgh. So, B has showed implicature and make A asked B for another day.

As example before, showed assumption in implicature is one of the keys to understand the implicature. The assumption also depends on circumstance contained in utterance. All of assumption in implicature called presupposition, and the circumstance utterance called context (Grice, 1975; Levinson, 1983; Yule, 1999). Both of them used for interpreting the meaning of implicature (Sosiowati: 2020).

Implicature can founded in many languages. Some of them are applied in society supported by social-culture background. In Japan, implicature motivated to the culture called *aimai*. *Aimai* must ambiguous to keeping participant feeling, and keep solidarity. For example, *chotto* in Japanese means ‘a little bit; wait for minute; a bit’ (Takoboto: 2023). But it can mean in many interpretations. *Chotto* can used for rejected an invitation, requesting, etc. Just say *chotto*, Japanese people can understand that speaker reject in indirectly. The conversation used *chotto* in Japanese which violated maxim showed below.

(1-2) Context: Akane, Aoi, and Chinatsu are just finished their club activity. Aoi invited Akane and Chinatsu to buy ice cream.

- | | | |
|----------|---|--|
| 葵 | : | コンビニへ行こうか？ |
| Aoi | : | <i>Konbini ikouka?</i> |
| Aoi | : | Let’s go to convenience store. |
| 千夏 | : | 行こう、行こう！ |
| Chinatsu | : | <i>Ikou! Ikou!</i> |
| Chinatsu | : | Let’s go! |
| 葵 | : | 今日何アイスしようかな。。 |
| Aoi | : | <i>Kyou nani aisu shiyou kana....</i> |
| Aoi | : | Today’s what flavor ice cream gonna eat? |
| 茜 | : | ああ、私。。。ちよつと。。 |
| Akane | : | <i>Aa, watashi chotto.....</i> |
| Akane | : | Ah, today Im wait..... |
| 葵 | : | え？用事？ |
| Aoi | : | <i>Ee? Youji?</i> |
| Aoi | : | Eh? You have task? |

(Anime *Tsuki Ga Kirei*, Episode 8, 06:28-06:46)

On dialog (1-2) implicature has showed in “*Aa, watashi chotto.....*” ‘**Ah, today Im wait.....**’. Akane was violated the maxim of relation because she didn’t relevance with Aoi’s speech. Aoi asked Chinatsu and Akane about the flavor of ice cream she will buy because the time of conversation in summer time. Meanwhile Akane stated word *chotto* means ‘wait’. As the order of Aoi speech, this speech order Chinatsu and Akane to answer their recommendation of flavor of ice cream. This is the reason why Akane not related with the utterance. But, the activity of violating maxim brought implicature which implied Akane just had another task to do and can’t go to convenience. There are several assumptions. First, Aoi assumed Chinatsu and Akane will go with her to convenience; (2) They had have go to convenience after club to buy ice cream before conversation showed in words *today*; (3) Akane assumed

Aoi and Chinatsu will understand that she have another task after club by saying *chotto*. Because of Aoi and Chinatsu understand what Akane means by implicature, showed by response in “*Ee youji*” ‘Eh? You have task?’ the implication was reached. Based on background, showed that floating maxim to make implicature is an interesting study. The research about implicature has been studied previously. Kusuma (2021) in “The Perlocutionary Effect in Conversational Implicature in Anime Tsuki Ga Kirei” discussed about perlocutionary effect caused by application of implicature. Kusuma (2021) used types of implicature arranged by Yule (1996) and speech act by Austin (1962). The results were particularized conversational implicature dominant used by characters in source data, and implicature forced perlocutionary to accept implication. Beside participant who know specific knowledge contained in implicature didn’t always accept the implication. Sometimes they can reject because between speaker and participant has different aims. Second, Tessa (2021) in “Implicature in Najwa Shihab Speech on Gelar Wicara Najwa Shihab Episode Ward of Corona and Waiting for Terawan” focused on speech act related to implicature on Najwa Shihab speech. The results were generalized conversational implicature were dominant used, and the function of implicature were assertive, directive, and expressive. Third, Yulianti et al (2022) “Conversational Implicature on Saturday Night Live Talk Show” studied about conversational implicature used in Saturday Night Live Talk Show. This research founded particularized conversational implicature dominant used, because reflected to particularized context while producing utterance to make conversation to meaningful and effective. All of literature reviews showed that implicature has many objects to studied. Those literatures become reference for next research. In this research focus on floating maxims in implicature in Japanese. Data sourced in *anime* (animation in Japan) and drama to looking for implicature. Only conversational implicature used for data because conventional implicature didn’t appear causing of violating of maxim. The four maxims by Grice (1975) used for analyzed theory.

METHOD AND RESEARCH THEORY

To collect data, observation method used to observe implicature data in dialog by all characters in *anime* and *drama* in Japanese. Observation method is one of methods to collect data by observe source data (Sugiyono, 2018: 229). Steps of collecting data were explained below.

1. After watched *anime* and drama, data was transcript with transcription technique.
2. Data were all of dialog by all characters which contained implicature.
3. Then, implicature categorized in maxim that violated based on four maxims by Grice (1975).

The theory used in this research was implicature by Grice (1975). As Levinson stated (1983), implicature is one of scopes studied in pragmatic. Based on studied in pragmatic, implicature find the speakers meaning. In implicature, there is conveyed meaning or the truth condition of the utterances. Speaker conscious to conveyed its meaning in utterance, delivered to participant to interpret the meaning. In implicature also contained presupposition, the assumption that have by speaker and participant.

In general, implicature divided in two group, conversational implicature and conventional implicature (Grice: 1975). In conversational implicature, occurred of violating maxim. This maxim is a principle of communication called cooperative principle, to bring good coordination between participant in exchange communication. Grice divided cooperative principle into four maxims. First, in maxim of quality speaker have to say what is believed to not false (Grice, 1975: 46). Second, maxim of quantitative make communication to not more informative as required (Grice, 1975: 45). Third, maxim of relation make speaker to make exchange conversation to be related, and relevant as aims of communication achieved (Grice, 1975: 46). And the fourth, maxim of manner arranged speaker to make conversation not ambiguous, and be brief (Grice, 1975: 46). After collected data, Data analyzed with matching method of pragmatic, which used participant response to be measuring instrument for analysis (Sudaryanto, 1993: 14). After analyzing data, data were presented by informal method which a method to presenting data in descriptive words (Sudaryanto, 1993: 145).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

According to the aim of this research to find the violating maxim in implicature used in Japanese, founded three maxims that violated in implicature. Speaker violated quantitative, relation, and manner maxim which dominant violated relation maxim. The domination of violating relation maxim causing by differences aim between speaker and participant. Those differences include incompatible desire, or influence participant to accept request. Implicature occurred by violating relation maxim showed below.

(1-3) Context: While followed her ex-boyfriend, Akane accidentally bumped someone.

- あかね : ごめんなさい。ちょっと冒頭したっていうのからですね。考えて事っていうか。ちょっと辛いことがあって、周りが見えてなくてですね。
- Akane : *Gomennasai. Chotto bouto shitatte iu no kara desune. Kangaete kototte iu ka. Chotto tsurai koto ga atte mawari ni mietenakute desune.*
- Akane : Sorry, I just stunned. There's something I thought. You know, something cruel so I didn't look around.
- 山田 : ほーそうっすか。
- Yamada : *Hoo...soussuka.*
- Yamada : Oh....I see.
- あかね : すみません。どうでもいいでしょうね。
- Akane : *Sumimasen. Dou demo ii deshoun?*
- Akane : Im sorry. I talked too much, right?
- 山田 : まあ。。興味はないっすね。
- Yamada : *Maa...kyoumi wa naissune*
- Yamada : **Yeah.... I didn't interest**
(Akane shocked)

(Yamada-Kun no Reberu 999 Koi wo Suru, Episode, 10:38-11:19)

In data (1-3), conversation happened because Akane accidentally bumped Yamada when she followed her ex-boyfriend in game festival. Akane was apologized and told Yamada that she had something problems, to make Yamada understanding her. Realizing of she was talked too much, Akane asked for apologized again. Meanwhile, Yamada said he didn't interest.

The utterance talked by Yamada was implicature, showed in "*Maa...kyoumi wa naissune*" 'Yeah.... I don't excited'. This implicature created by violating maxim by Yamada which violated relation maxim. The relation maxim expected partner to contribute in appropriated as needed (Grice, 1975: 47). This make partner giving response as relate as communication required in the exchange communication.

As Akane stated in (1-3), she asked apologized because she thought that she talked to much for him. The utterances was stated in interrogative mode pointed by "*....deshoun?*" 'right?'. By this utterances Akane wanted a contribution for giving response by *yes* or *no*. Akane expected that she gave to much information which not related with him, and assumed Yamada will understanding her. Meanwhile, Yamada didn't give appropriated response by "*Maa...kyoumi wa naissune*" 'Yeah.... I don't excited'. The violating of maxim implied that Yamada didn't care about Akane's problems, and Akane didn't need to explain him.

(1-4) Context: Akane brought home food for Yamada because she wanted to say thanks for invited Akane to the game group.

- 山田 : この思い荷物なんですか。
- Yamada : *Kono omoi nimotsu nan desuka?*
- Yamada : What is that heavy bag?

あかね : はああ。。これはね、カレー当世を米はないのだから、ルートしたごはんも持ってきた。今朝作ったバカのカレーだから、二日食べられるよ。私今月ピンチだから、お肉をあんま入ってないけど。。その代わりに、先コンビニに買ったサラダと福神漬けをくれてやろう！

Akane : *Haaaa....kore wa ne, karee...Tousei o kome wa nai no darou kara, ruuto shita gohan mo motte kita. Kesa tsukutta baka no karee dakara, futsuka taberareruyo. Watashi kongetsu pinchi dakara oniku wa anma haittenai dakedo.....sono kawari ni, saki konbini ni katta sarada to fukujinzuke wo kurete yarou!*

Akane : Haaa....its kare. I just thought you didn't have rice, so I bought rice for you. Also, because I made it this morning, you can eat for two days. I'm in crisis now, sorry for not much meat in it. For exchange, I give you salad and pickles I bought in convenience.

山田 : いや。あの。。。悪いけど、いいすよ。しかも、金がないですよ。

Yamada : *Iya. Ano...Warui kara, iisuyo. Shikamo, kane ga nai desuyone.*

Yamada : No. Sorry, but its oke. Instead, you said you didn't have money right?

あかね : **ちゃんと食べないと、大きくなれないよ。。。。**

Akane : ***Chanto tabenaito, ookiku narenaiyo...***

Akane : **If you don't eat properly, you can't grow well.**

山田 : いや。まあ。。。。

Yamada : *Iya. Maa.....*

Yamada : But....oke.... (accepted Akane's given)

(Anime Yamada-kun no Reberu 999 Koi wo Suru, Episode 4,18:28-19:05)

The context of data (1-4) Akane was grateful because Yamada accepted her to join game group. When Akane go to convenience store with Yamada, she saw Yamada bought pudding and told her that pudding will be his dinner. Akane asked him why he don't cook for his dinner. Yamada told he can't cook. After that, Akane quickly going home to pack some food for Yamada. She thought it's a great time to say thanks for him because he had invited her to game group. In other side, Yamada felt hesitated because Akane was told him she's in crisis. To make him accepted her food, Akane said if he doesn't eat properly, Yamada can't growth up.

The action of asking Akane by "*Iya. Ano...Warui kara, iisuyo. Shikamo, kane ga nai desuyone*" 'No. Sorry, but its oke. Instead, you said you didn't have money right?', there is two assumption in that utterance. First, Yamada know Akane still in crisis because she was told him. Second, if she gives him food, Akane will be in problem because she is in crisis. The interrogative mode by utterance bring *yes* or *no* response as utterance required. Instead, Akane didn't give *yes* or *no* as conversation settle. She said "***Chanto tabenaito, ookiku narenaiyo...***" '**If you don't eat properly, you can't grow well**'. The utterance is not related to the conversation and make violating of relation maxim (Grice, 1975: 47). The violating of maxim caused by Yamada that tried to reject Akane's food. It also factored by Akane was assumed that Yamada didn't eat well recently because he is busy with university entrance examination. Especially, he is living alone and can't make food by himself. By its implicature, Akane was implied to make Yamada took her food and didn't feel hesitate. As showed in (1-4), in the end Yamada took the food that showed implication was influenced him.

(1-5) Context: Akane curious her necklace was dropped in Yamada's house when she got drunk. She's upset because the necklace got from her ex-boyfriend.

あかね : それで思い出した。タクマのネックレスどうしよう。山田の家で落とした思うだけどなあ。

Akane : *Sore de omoidashita Takuma no nekkuresu dou shiyou? Yamada no ie de otoshita omou dakedo naa..*

Akane : How about the necklace from Takuma? I think it dropped in Yamada's house.

モモ : 自分の捨てた男プレゼントになんのがある？未練がましい。茜ってそういうところがあるよね。要諦は全部彼氏に優先にするし、彼氏に合わせて興味はないネットゲーム始めるし。そういうば、付き合っすぐに作り弁当事が作った。絶対的に思い込んだよな。。。。

Momo : *Jibun wo suteta otoko puresento ni nannoyo ga aru? Mirengamashii. Akanette sou iu toko ga aru yo ne. Youtei wa zenbu kareshi ni yuusen ni suru shi, kareshi ni awasete kyoomi wa nai netto geemu hajimerushi. Sou ieba, tsukiatte sugu ni tsukuri bentou koto ga tsukutta. Zettai teki ni omoindayone...*

Momo : **What the hell you think about present gave by your ex? So unwilling. As always Akane. Always prioritized your boyfriend, to match with him you started to play game which not your interest. Anyway, I remember. After going out you immediately cooked for him.**

茜 : もうタクマの話しないで、許してください。

Akane : *Mou Takuma no hanashi shinai node, yurushite kudasai.*

Akane : I don't talk about Takuma again. Sorry.

(*Anime Yamada-kun no Reberu 999 Koi wo Suru*, Episode 2, 10:58-11:35)

Data in (1-5) showed Akane was talking with her friend, Momo about her necklace which lost in Yamada's house, when she got drunk. Akane was worried because she lost her necklace got from her ex-boyfriend and confused how to ask Yamada for the necklace, because they don't close. Momo who know Akane's ex-boyfriend was cheated on Akane, felt annoyed when she heard that Akane was worried about the necklace. So, when Akane asked her opinion about what should she do about necklace, Momo stated an utterance which no correlation as asked. According to the response, bring an implicature.

Implicature showed in "*Jibun wo suteta otoko puresento ni nannoyo ga aru? Mirengamashii. Akanette sou iu toko ga aru yo ne. Youtei wa zenbu kareshi ni yuusen ni suru shi, kareshi ni awasete kyoumi wa nai netto geemu hajimerushi. Sou ieba, tsukiatte sugu ni tsukuri bentou koto ga tsukutta. Zettai teki ni omoindayone...*" 'What the hell you think about present gave by your ex? So unwilling. As always Akane. Always prioritized your boyfriend, to match with him you started to play game which not your interest. Anyway, I remember. After going out you immediately cooked for him'. Grice stated implicature created by violating maxim (1975). As the data in (1-5), Momo was violating a manner maxim. The manner maxim request speaker to be brief, and not give ambiguous state (Grice: 1975). Also, the implicature was violated relation maxim because the utterance is not relevant with Akane asked (Grice: 1975). As manner and relation maxim required, Momo must to response the asking of "*Takuma no nekkuresu dou shiyou?*" 'How about Takuma's necklace' with an advice like "Go ask Yamada" or "You have to check it first".

In (1-5), Akane was assumed that Momo will give her advice, but Momo gave her a long explain, no brief that no correlation. Beside of that, Momo assumed that Akane was over kind with her ex-boyfriend instead she was cheated by her ex. That's made her to give a lot of her lack side when she loved her boyfriend to much without thinking about being cheated in the future. Momo just want to make Akane realized that she would have to forget about her ex, including all of his given for her. In data (1-5), Akane realized Momo satirized her and said that she promises not talking about her ex again. This response giving a point that implication well interpreted by Akane.

(1-6) Context: Hinako and Hiroto discussed about Hinako speech as new president of company. Accidentally, Hinako saw news about Hiroto's agreement with America's company. Meanwhile, he just met with that company several times ago.

雛子 : 何ですかこれ。

Hiroto : *Nan desuka kore?*

Hiroto : What is it? (pointing on news in tablet)

寛人 : ああ。先決めたんだよ。

Hiroto : *Aa. Saki kimetandayo.*

Hiroto : Aa. I just decided.

雛子 : さっき? わあ。。すごい決断力だね。

Hinako : *Sakki? Wa...sugoi ketsudanryoku dane.*

Hinako : **Just decided? Wa...how great your decisiveness.**

(Hiroto smile)

(*Muchaburi! Watashi ga Shachou ni Naru Nante!* Episode 2, 03:10-03:20)

The participant in dialog (1-6) is Hinako and Hiroto who talking about Hinako's speech as new president in their company. Hiroto was promoted Hinako as president which previously been his secretary. Because of Hinako didn't have any experience as president,

she was confused with her speech and Hiroto tried to help her with giving some advice. Actually, Hinako didn't want to be promoted but she forced to be president. As long as Hiroto revised her speech, Hinako realized that she will have to do more practice. In the middle of discussion, Hinako saw a news about corporation between their company with America's company. Hinako aghast because as she knows, Hiroto have not yet decided on the outcome meeting. She thought Hiroto really great in decisiveness, like president must have.

The utterance of "*Sakki? Wa...sugoi ketsudanryoku dane*" 'Just decided? Wa...how great your decisiveness' is an implicature. It was created by violating maxim of quantitative maxim. The violating of quantitative maxim bring much information than needed in conversation (Grice: 1975). As data (1-6), Hinako asked Hiroto for the news and Hiroto told her that he just decided for the project. When participant do the exchange communication, Hinako have to response the utterance "*Aa. Saki kimetandayo*" 'I just decided' with "Oh I see" to contribute as quantitative maxim required. But the violating maxim to give more information than needed provide other information that conveyed in implicature. The implicature has two assumption. First, Hiroto's good decisiveness is not first time, and Hinako already know it because she was his ex-secretary. On those assumption, implied that Hiroto has often handle meeting project and has a lot of experience so he has good decisiveness as president must have. For those implicature Hiroto just smile to response it, means he understand with its implication.

CONCLUSION

According to the results and discussion, this research discussed about the violating maxim on implicature in Japanese. The violating maxim in implicature were maxim of relation, manner, and quantitative. The relation maxim was dominant founded. The function of violating maxim was to make the aims of communication reached, so speaker have to violated the maxim and created implicature. In other side, the violating maxim used because sometimes speaker has different aims with their partner. It also make partners have more information in communication. Floating of relation maxim used for showing disinterest, admiration, and sarcasm.

REFERENCES

1. Grice, H.P. 1975. Logic and Conversation. University of California.
2. Horn, L.R. 2004. Implicature. The Handbook of Pragmatics. Eds Horn, L.R and Ward, G. Blackwell Publishing.
3. Kusuma, N.M.Y.W and Pradhana, I.N. "The Perlocutionary Effect on Conversational Implicature in Anime Tsuki Ga Kirei". Journal of SAKURA, 2021, in press.
4. Levinson, S.C. 1983. Pragmatics. Cambridge University Press.
5. Morris, C. 1938. Foundations of Theory of Signs. University of Chicago Press.
6. Saul, J. 2010. Speaker-Meaning, Conversational Implicature and Calculability. Eds Richard Breheny & Nicole Gotzner. Palgrave Studies in Pragmatics, Language and Cognition, 170-183. Palgrave Macmillan.
7. Searle, J.R. 1979. Expression and Meaning: Studies in Theory of Speech Acts. Cambridge University Press.
8. Sosiowati, I.G.A.G. 2021. The Importance of Context of Situation in Deciding The Meaning of An Utterance. In proceeding of Kongres Internasional Masyarakat Linguistik Indonesia.
9. Sudaryanto. 1993. Metode dan Aneka Teknik Analisis Bahasa (Pengantar Penelitian Wahana Kebudayaan Secara Linguistik). Duta Wacana University Press.
10. Sugiyono. 2018. Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, R&D. Alfabeta.
11. Takoboto. 2023. Access on <https://takoboto.jp/>.
12. Tessa, Q. A. 2021. Implikatur dalam Tuturan Najwa Shihab pada Acara Gelar Mata Najwa Episode Menangkal Corona dan Menanti Terawan. Master thesis., University of Andalas.
13. Yule, G. 1996. *Pragmatics*. Oxford University Press.
14. Yulianti, S et al. "Conversational Implicatures on Saturday Night Live Talk Show". Journal of Language Teaching and Research, 2022, in press.

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